

Homomorphic WiSARDs: Efficient Weightless Neural Network training over encrypted data

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ABSTRACT

The widespread application of machine learning algorithms is a matter of increasing concern for the data privacy research community, and many have sought to develop privacy-preserving techniques for it. Among the existing approaches, the homomorphic evaluation of machine learning algorithms stands out by performing operations directly over encrypted data, enabling strong and inherent guarantees of confidentiality. The HE evaluation of inference algorithms is already practical even for relatively deep Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs). However, training is still a major challenge, with current solutions often resorting to interactive protocols or lightweight algorithms, which can be unfit for accurately solving more complex problems, such as image recognition.

In this work, we introduce the homomorphic evaluation of Wilkie, Stonham, and Aleksander’s Recognition Device (WiSARD) and subsequent state-of-the-art Weightless Neural Networks (WNNs) both for training and inference on homomorphically encrypted data. Compared to CNNs, WNNs offer much better performance with a relatively small accuracy deterioration. We develop a complete framework for it, including several building blocks that can be of independent interest. Our framework achieves 91.71% accuracy on the MNIST dataset after only 3.5 minutes of encrypted training (multi-threaded), going up to 93.76% in 3.5 hours after training over 60 thousand images. For the HAM10000 dataset, we achieve 67.85% accuracy in just 1.5 minutes, going up to 69.85% after 1 hour. Compared to the state of the art on HE evaluation of CNN training, Glyph (Lou *et al.*, NeurIPS 2020), these results represent a speedup of up to 1200 times with an accuracy loss of at most 5.4%. For HAM10000, we even achieved a 0.65% accuracy improvement while being 60 times faster than Glyph. We also provide solutions for small-scale encrypted training. In a single thread on a consumer Desktop machine using less than 200MB of memory, we train over 1000 MNIST images in 12 minutes or over the entire Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset in just 11 seconds.

KEYWORDS

homomorphic encryption, neural network training, WiSARD, training over encrypted data, weightless neural networks, privacy-preserving machine learning,

1 INTRODUCTION

The popularization of machine learning (ML) in modern data processing applications brought with itself a great concern over the privacy implications of its widespread use, which often requires large-scale data collection or processing of sensitive information. As a result, privacy-preserving machine learning became a topic of broad research interest, and many solutions have been proposed on different fronts of this issue. Among them, homomorphic encryption (HE) has long been considered one of the most powerful tools for enabling privacy for data during processing, as it enables operations to be performed directly over encrypted data. It comes, however, with a significant computational performance overhead, which has often been an impairment for the HE evaluation of large ML models.

The most successful use cases so far are in the HE evaluation of inference algorithms based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [22, 27, 29]. Thanks to techniques such as quantized training [33] and FHE-friendly activation functions [28], modern HE schemes are capable of efficiently evaluating inferences while achieving near state-of-the-art accuracy. Efficient and accurate encrypted training, on the other hand, remains mostly an open problem, as current solutions either stay far from state-of-the-art accuracy levels or take weeks of computation to be run [35]. Some scenarios allow for alternative approaches, such as client-assisted FHE [11] and other MPC-based protocols. These commonly offer good results in limited contexts, but they come with the intrinsic downsides of a multi-party protocol.

Other solutions rely on techniques such as transfer learning and cleartext feature extraction, in which a pre-trained model or feature extraction algorithm is applied over the unencrypted input data before the encrypted training. This approach has often been employed to accelerate or improve the accuracy of encrypted training [31, 35, 41]. However, its application is limited as it requires the existence of a pre-trained model that works for the specific problem. This model needs to be trained and evaluated on cleartext, requiring additional security and usability assumptions. It requires, for example, the client (data owner) to perform part of the training (the feature extraction) on cleartext in a trusted environment before encrypting the input data, which might be prohibitive in the case of resource-constrained clients.

For end-to-end fully encrypted training, the most practical approaches so far go in the direction of adopting simpler ML algorithms or methods for switching between different HE schemes. In 2019, NRPH19 [40] presented the first stochastic-gradient-descent-based (SGD) approach for encrypted NN training, achieving accuracies of 85.9% up to 97.8% on inferences on the MNIST dataset [30]. Their execution time, however, would be up to more than a decade (as estimated in [35]). Using HE scheme switching, Chimera [6, 7] and Glyph [35], improved this result significantly, enabling accuracies of 94.1% up to 97.1% with execution times between 5.7 and 28.6 days¹ for the former and between 1.5 and 8 days for the latter. Recently, MFK+24 [39] presented a TFHE [16]-based evaluation of a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) training for the Wisconsin breast cancer dataset [48], achieving 98.25% accuracy in 49 minutes.

1.1 Overview and Contributions

In this work, we follow the general idea of evaluating alternative NN models to introduce the HE evaluation of Weightless Neural Networks (WNNs). In contrast with typical NNs, neurons of WNNs are Random Access Memory units (RAMs), which evaluate arbitrary functions over the data they receive. There are no weights or biases, and the training consists of programming the RAM units to evaluate different functions that will (hopefully) recognize categorizing patterns in the input data. One of the most basic instantiations of a WNN and our starting point in this work is Wilkie, Stonham, and Aleksander’s Recognition Device (WiSARD) [3]. In their model, RAM units are programmed to simply output whether or not a certain pattern of bits (the neuron’s input) was present in the training set for a certain label. Modern WNNs employ significantly more complex functions than this, but the basic principle of programming RAM units remains their defining aspect.

Our work starts from the observation that operating with RAM units fits perfectly well within the HE evaluation model provided by schemes such as FHEW [18] and TFHE [16], which are based on the evaluation of lookup tables (LUTs).

1.1.1 Evaluation model. The main aspect determining the characteristics of a WNN is the type of RAM it implements. The original WiSARD model adopted binary RAMs, *i.e.*, each address of the RAM stores a single bit, and, hence, the RAM of each neuron can only indicate whether a pattern occurred or not. Subsequent WNNs adopted a *bleaching technique* that uses integers as RAM elements followed by a threshold function. In this case, each address counts the number of occurrences of a pattern and, at the end of the training, a threshold function binarizes the elements based on some fixed value. Modern WNNs employ a variety of techniques to implement RAMs, including, *e.g.*, Bloom filters and SGD-adjusted scores.

In this work, our first step is to represent WNNs in a model that can be efficiently homomorphically evaluated. For this, we generalize the bleaching technique approach and formalize the concepts of the Integer WiSARD model and model activation phases. The basic working principle remains the same, we use integer RAMs to count every occurrence of a pattern and apply a non-linear function over the RAMs once training is finished. The main differences lie in the

separation of the process into two procedures and in the generalization of bleaching to allow the performing of arbitrary activation functions. Our main motivation for this is to separate arithmetic (integer counting) from non-arithmetic (model activation) computation, which not only facilitates the HE evaluation but also enables us to introduce several optimizations of independent techniques for each procedure. Nonetheless, our approach also brings advantages for the evaluation of WNNs in general. The use of activation functions other than just threshold binarization allows us to implement other types of WNNs following the same principle. It also allows us to consider alternative activation functions to improve the average accuracy. Additionally, the Integer WiSARD model training, as a standalone procedure, is trivially parallelizable and enables us to easily define protocols for distributed and federated learning.

1.1.2 Encrypted Model Inference. We introduce the HE evaluation of WNN inference algorithms using the TFHE scheme [16]. Compared to other existing practical solutions for NN inference over encrypted data, our approach has the advantage of providing model privacy, as our evaluation method can work with an encrypted model with minimal additional cost. It also significantly advances the state of the art on TFHE-based NN inference [45].

TFHE introduced procedures such as programmable bootstrapping [17] and vertical packing [16], which enable the evaluation of arbitrary functions by representing them as lookup tables. Thanks to this, the scheme is often highlighted as one of the most promising schemes for NN applications. Realizing this potential, however, has shown to be a challenge, as most of its current applications struggle to provide low inference latency due to the combination of arithmetic and non-arithmetic procedures of typical NN. Our evaluation model for WNNs avoids this problem, and we improve the performance of state-of-the-art TFHE-based inference [45] more than 300 times.

1.1.3 Encrypted Model Training. Our main focus and contribution is the introduction of a framework to allow the efficient homomorphic evaluation of WNN training. We perform training encrypted end to end, without using any pre-processing techniques that would require knowledge of the full data set. Our evaluation approach relies on two building blocks that we introduce for the TFHE scheme:

- A homomorphic controlled demultiplexer gate (**CDEMUX**), that performs the inverse operation of TFHE’s multiplexer gate (CMUX [16]) with similar operands.
- An **Inverse Vertical Packing (IVP)** technique, based on the controlled demultiplexer gate (CDEMUX) and other operations of TFHE, which produces or updates a LUT, from which one may later evaluate using TFHE’s Vertical Packing (VP) [15] technique.

Our homomorphic evaluation of the training procedure excels not only for its practical results in terms of performance and accuracy but also for its versatility and the simplicity of its implementation. Particularly, we show it can be easily employed in scenarios such as distributed, federated [49], and continuous [42] learning. We also define additional procedures, such as an efficient method for homomorphically performing dataset balancing.

1.1.4 Implementation and Results. We benchmark our construction over the main datasets used in the literature, and we show

¹From Glyph results.

significant improvements in encrypted training performance with a small impact on the accuracy. We provide several options for training parameters that trade off accuracy and performance. For the MNIST dataset, our solutions enable accuracy varying from 91.71% up to 93.76% with execution time from just 3.5 minutes up to 3.5 hours. This represents a significant performance improvement over previous literature (which would take from 1.5 to 8 days) at the cost of an accuracy drop of 2.5% to 5.4%. For the HAM10000 dataset [47], we improve both performance and accuracy compared to previous literature, achieving 67.85% to 69.85% accuracy with encrypted training time varying from 1.5 minutes up to 1 hour. Compared to Glyph [35], this represents an accuracy improvement of 0.65% with a performance improvement of 60 times (already adjusting for differences in the execution environment).

We provide an open-source proof-of-concept implementation of training and evaluation procedures based on the MOSFET [25] library, available at <https://github.com/leonardohn/homomorphic-wisards>.

1.1.5 Further Improvements. We see end-to-end encrypted training as the major challenge for enabling practical privacy-preserving machine learning. Therefore, this work focuses strictly on this problem, without further exploring techniques that would improve accuracy or performance but also require additional assumptions (e.g., transfer learning, client-assisted training, and multi-party protocols). Nonetheless, it is important to notice that these techniques are not alternatives to our proposals. On the contrary, they are context-specific optimizations that could be applied over WNNs in similar ways as they are for general neural networks. Transfer learning, for example, which has been shown to bring significant improvements for the encrypted training of CNNs [31, 35, 41], could also be straightforwardly applied to WNNs [38] for problems in which it fits. The same can be said for client-assisted computation, which can generally be used to accelerate most HE workloads.

Paper Structure. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the relevant theoretical basis. Section 3 introduces the Homomorphic WiSARD architecture. Section 4 presents our results, comparing with the current state of the art. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Notation

Let \mathbb{Z} be the set of integer numbers and \mathcal{R} be a polynomial ring $\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{Z}[X]/(X^N + 1)$ with coefficients in \mathbb{Z} modulo some power-of-two cyclotomic polynomial $(X^N + 1)$. We use subscript to denote their moduli and superscript to denote the number of dimensions, for example \mathbb{Z}_q^n is the set of vectors of size n with elements in $\mathbb{Z}/q\mathbb{Z}$ (the integers modulo q). For clarity, we use brackets to index neural network models represented as multidimensional matrices, and subscript to index everything else (e.g., list, vectors, and tuples). We denote Uniform and Gaussian sampling with mean zero and standard deviation σ from some group \mathbb{G} respectively as $x \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathbb{G}$ and $x \xleftarrow{\text{G}(\sigma)} \mathbb{G}$.

2.2 Weightless Neural Networks

Weightless Neural Networks (WNNs) (also known as N -tuple classifiers [5] or *RAMnets*) are one of the oldest neural network-like algorithms ever created for image recognition. Training and inference are entirely based on programming Random Access Memory units (RAMs), which are mutable n -bit input, 2^n -output lookup tables, that may be configured to behave as any discrete function.

By itself, a single RAM could already be considered a classification algorithm. It can learn discrete functions by adjusting their outputs in response to input-output pairs from a target function and evaluate any discrete function in constant time. This expressiveness, however, comes with the downside that the RAM size doubles for every bit we add to the input, quickly becoming infeasible for large inputs. As there might be no representing samples for certain input permutations in a training set, RAMs are also unable to generalize over unseen inputs.

2.3 WiSARD Model

In this work, we start with one of the most basic instances of a WNN: the Wilkie, Stonham, and Aleksander’s Recognition Device (WiSARD) [3]. Created to address the limitations of freestanding RAMs, the WiSARD model organizes multiple RAMs into structures denoted discriminators. Each discriminator partitions the input into k n -bit tuples, which are fed into k distinct RAMs. The combined outputs from the RAMs of a discriminator, denoted as the score, quantify the recognized sub-patterns present in the input. In a classification problem, each discriminator represents a class, and the class corresponding to the discriminator with the highest score is taken as the prediction. Definition 1 describes a generic version of the WiSARD model for classification problems. For the original model, \mathbb{G} is the set of binary numbers \mathbb{B} .

DEFINITION 1 (GENERIC WISARD MODEL). *Given a classification problem for input samples of bit size (s) and (l) classes, a Generic WiSARD model $\mathcal{W}_{(s,l,a,r)}$ with address size (a) and random seed (r) is a matrix in $\mathbb{G}^{l \times k \times 2^a}$ with elements in some group \mathbb{G} . It comprises l discriminators, such that each discriminator is a tuple of $k = \lceil s / a \rceil$ RAMs, and each RAM is a tuple of 2^a elements in \mathbb{G} . Let $\pi_r : \mathbb{B}^s \mapsto \mathbb{B}^s$ be a pseudo-random bit permutation map deterministic on the value r , and $f_{\text{comp}} : \mathbb{B}^s \times \mathbb{Z} \mapsto \mathbb{Z}_{2^a}$ be a composition function given by $f_{\text{comp}}(x, d) = \sum_{i=0}^{\text{MIN}(a,s-ad)} x_{i+ad} 2^i$, Algorithms 1 and 2 define the training and evaluation for \mathcal{W} , respectively.*

The basic idea behind the inference using the WiSARD model is that each RAM would recognize small bit patterns to classify the input. Notice that, during training, each discriminator receives only samples from its respective label, learning to identify these small bit patterns. During the evaluation phase, the input is presented to all discriminators in the model, each producing a score based on the values provided by their RAMs. Figures 1 and 2a depict the entire inference process and examples of a discriminator with input size $s = 4$ and address size $a = 2$, respectively.

2.4 State-of-the-art WNNs

The WiSARD model was first introduced in 1984 as a commercial version of the N -tuple classification algorithm from 1959 [5]. Since then, many techniques have been introduced to improve the

Algorithm 1: Training of a WiSARD model

Input : a WiSARD model $\mathcal{W}_{(s,l,a,r)}$
Input : a training set T of size n and its list of labels L
Output : trained WiSARD model

- 1 $\mathcal{W} \leftarrow \{0\}; r \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}; k \leftarrow \lceil s/a \rceil$
- 2 **for** $i \in \llbracket 0, n \rrbracket$ **do**
- 3 $t \leftarrow \pi_r(T_i)$
- 4 **for** $j \in \llbracket 0, k \rrbracket$ **do**
- 5 $d \leftarrow f_{\text{comp}}(t, j)$
- 6 $\mathcal{W}[L_i][j][d] \leftarrow 1$
- 7 **return** \mathcal{W}

Algorithm 2: Evaluate a sample in a WiSARD model

Input : a WiSARD Model $\mathcal{W}_{(s,l,a,r)}$
Input : a sample t
Output : classification of t

- 1 $k \leftarrow \lceil s/a \rceil; t' \leftarrow \pi_r(t)$
- 2 **for** $j \in \llbracket 0, k \rrbracket$ **do**
- 3 $u_j \leftarrow \sum_{i=0}^k \mathcal{W}[j][i][f_{\text{comp}}(t', i)]$
- 4 **return** $\text{ARGMAX}(u)$

Figure 1: Evaluation of a WiSARD model.

WiSARD model and, more generally, Weightless Neural Network algorithms. This section discusses some of them.

2.4.1 Bleaching. Bleaching [23] is a technique used in the WiSARD model to adjust the sensitiveness of the model to repeated sub-patterns in the training set. It consists of replacing the RAMs binary values with integers, which now counts how many times small bit patterns are seen during the training phase.

During the evaluation phase, a threshold operator is applied to every RAM output value, resulting in a binary value that will be used to produce the score. This adjustment can significantly improve

the accuracy of models with smaller address sizes. In Figure 2b we illustrate the evaluation of a discriminator with bleaching.

Figure 2: Evaluation of two discriminators.

2.4.2 Quantization. Quantization [21] is a (possibly lossy) transformation constraining input values from a continuous or otherwise large set of values to a discrete, typically smaller set. Examples of quantization functions are as follows.

- **Linear:** $f_r(x) = \lfloor x/r \rfloor$, for a constant ratio r .
- **Logarithmic:** $f_b(x) = \lfloor \log_b(x+1) \rfloor$, for a base b .

The simplest form is linear quantization, where the input values are mapped to uniformly distributed values along the output domain. Other methods include logarithmic and Gaussian quantization, which can be beneficial when the sample density distribution is known. Choosing a distribution that better distinguishes values along key regions in the value space may help minimize the inherent rounding error introduced by this transformation.

2.4.3 Thermometer Encoding. Thermometer encoding [12], sometimes referred to as unary encoding, represents natural numbers, starting from zero, as increasing sequences of bits with value one. A thermometer $\mathcal{T}_N : \mathbb{N} \mapsto \mathbb{B}^N$ encodes a value $x \in \mathbb{N}$ into a vector $t = \mathcal{T}_N(x)$ such that $t_i = 1$ for $i \in [0, x]$, and $t_i = 0$ for $i \in [x, N)$. For instance, $\mathcal{T}_4(3) = [1, 1, 1, 0]$ and $\mathcal{T}_4(1) = [1, 0, 0, 0]$. The name comes from the resemblance to a thermometer, which fills in response to a temperature increase.

2.5 Homomorphic Encryption

Homomorphic encryption (HE) is a technique that allows computation over encrypted data by establishing a map (homomorphism) between operations over the ciphertexts and the messages they encrypt. It provides confidentiality guarantees as traditional encryption schemes, fully protecting data during computation. Most of the modern HE schemes are based on the Learning With Errors (LWE) [44] problem and its ring variant (RLWE) [37].

2.5.1 TFHE Scheme. We opt to work with the TFHE [16] scheme, as it presents techniques for efficiently evaluating lookup tables which are a perfect match for WiSARD's RAM-based logic. Furthermore, as we will show in Section 3, it can also be used to efficiently

generate RAM units during training. In this work, we only use a subset of the operations the scheme provides, which we define in the following.

- **SETUP**(λ): Security parameters $(q, N, n, \sigma_0, \sigma_1)$ are defined based on the plaintext space \mathbb{Z}_p , on the circuit to be homomorphically evaluated, and on security level, which we estimate using the Lattice Estimator [2]. The polynomial ring \mathcal{R} is defined as $\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{Z}[X]/(X^N + 1)$.
- **SECRETKEYGEN**(N, n): Given the lattices dimensions n and N , it samples an LWE key $S_0 \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathbb{B}^n$ and an RLWE key $S_1 \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathcal{R}_2$ and returns a pair of keys (S_0, S_1) .
- **Encryption**:
 - **EncLWE**(m, S_0, σ_0): Given the LWE secret key S_0 , a message $m \in \mathbb{Z}_p$, and noise parameter σ_0 , it samples $a \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathbb{Z}_q^n$ and $e \xleftarrow{G(\sigma_0)} \mathbb{Z}_q$, and computes $b \leftarrow \langle a, S_0 \rangle + m \frac{q}{p} + e$ to produce the LWE ciphertext $(a, b) \in \text{LWE}_{S_0}(m)$.
 - **EncRLWE**(m, S_1, σ_1): Given the RLWE secret key S_1 , a message $m \in \mathcal{R}_p$, and noise parameter σ_1 , it samples $a \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathcal{R}_q$ and $e \xleftarrow{G(\sigma_1)} \mathcal{R}_q$, and computes $b \leftarrow a \cdot S_1 + m \frac{q}{p} + e$ to produce the RLWE ciphertext $(a, b) \in \text{RLWE}_{S_1}(m)$.
 - **EncRGSW**(m, S_1, σ_1): Given the RLWE secret key S_1 , a message $m \in \mathcal{R}_p$, a noise parameter σ_1 , and decomposition parameters ℓ and β , it produces a vector $C \in \mathcal{R}_q^{2\ell \times 2}$ of 2ℓ RLWE ciphertexts encrypting 0's and a gadget decomposition matrix $G = \left[\left[0, \frac{q}{p\beta^0} \right], \dots, \left[0, \frac{q}{p\beta^{\ell-1}} \right], \left[\frac{q}{p\beta^0}, 0 \right], \dots, \left[\frac{q}{p\beta^{\ell-1}}, 0 \right] \right] \in \mathcal{R}_q^{2\ell \times 2}$. It returns the RGSW ciphertext given by $(C + m \cdot G) \in \text{RGSW}_{S_1}(m)$.
- **Decryption**:
 - **DecLWE**($c = (a, b), S_0$): Returns $\left\lfloor \frac{b - \langle a, S_0 \rangle}{q/p} \right\rfloor$
 - **DecRLWE**($c = (a, b), S_1$): Returns $\left\lfloor \frac{b - a \cdot S_1}{q/p} \right\rfloor$
 - **DecRGSW**($c = (c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{2\ell-1}), S_1$): Returns **DecRLWE**(c_0, S_1)
- **Evaluation**:
 - **Addition** ($c_0 + c_1$): Given ciphertexts c_0 and c_1 of the same type encrypting messages m_0 and m_1 , it returns a ciphertext encrypting $m_0 + m_1$.
 - **Multiplication** ($C_0 \boxtimes c_1$): Given an RGSW ciphertext C_0 and an RLWE ciphertext c_1 encrypting messages m_0 and m_1 , respectively, it returns an RLWE ciphertext encrypting $m_0 \cdot m_1$.
 - **CMUX**(C_0, c_1, c_2): Given an RGSW ciphertext C_0 and RLWE ciphertexts c_1 and c_2 encrypting messages $m_0 \in \{0, 1\}$, $m_1 \in \mathcal{R}_p$ and $m_2 \in \mathcal{R}_p$, respectively, it returns an RLWE ciphertext encrypting $m_0 \cdot m_1 + (1 - m_0) \cdot m_2$, which represents the computation of a selection (multiplexer) between m_1 and m_2 with selector m_0 .
 - **ExtractLWE**(c_0, i): Given an integer i and an RLWE ciphertext c_0 encrypting a polynomial $v = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} m_j X^j$ under key S , it returns an LWE ciphertext encrypting m_i .

- **PackingKeySwitching**(c): Given a vector of k LWE ciphertexts c with each of them encrypting a message $m_i \in \mathbb{Z}_p$, returns an RLWE ciphertext encrypting the polynomial $\sum_{i=0}^k m_i X^i \in \mathcal{R}_p$.
- **BlindRotate**(c, C, I): Given a vector of k RGSW ciphertexts C with each of them encrypting a binary message $S_i \in \mathbb{B}$, a vector of k integers I , a RLWE ciphertext c encrypting a polynomial v , the **BlindRotate** returns an RLWE ciphertext $c' \in \text{RLWE} \left(v X^{-\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} S_i I_i} \right)$, which is negacyclic rotation of v .

We only define the operations we use in this paper, and we treat them as black-box procedures all those in which the inner details do not affect our proposals. For more details about the TFHE scheme, refer to [15] and [16]. In the HE literature, ciphertexts are commonly referred to as “*samples*”, a term that is also used in the ML literature to refer to data objects that are input to a machine learning algorithm. To avoid confusion, we use the term “*sample*” only for the input data of an ML algorithm and not for ciphertexts.

2.5.2 LUT Evaluation. The main feature provided by TFHE is the efficient homomorphic evaluation of lookup tables (LUTs), which can represent any discretized function. TFHE presents two main methods for LUT evaluation, which we describe in the following.

Vertical Packing (VP). [15]: Let C be a list of RGSW ciphertext encrypting bit by bit the input $g \in \mathbb{B}^s$ to some function $f : \mathbb{B}^s \mapsto \mathbb{Z}_p$, the vertical evaluates f as follows:

- (1) **Function encoding**: Let $v \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{2^s}$ be a vector of evaluations of f such that $v_i = f(i)$ for all $i \in \mathbb{B}^s$, it encrypts v in a vector of $\lceil s/N \rceil$ RLWE ciphertexts L , such that each RLWE ciphertext L_i encrypts the polynomial $\sum_{j=0}^N v_{iN+j} X^j$.
- (2) **CMUX tree**: Let \bar{C} be a vector given by the first $\lceil \log_2(s/N) \rceil$ elements of C , and given the encrypted LUT L , the CMUX tree is defined in lines 2 to 6 of Algorithm 3. The vertical packing uses the CMUX tree to select the RLWE sample containing the desired position, L_0 .
- (3) **BLINDROTATE and result extraction**: Let \underline{C} be the vector given by the last $\log_2(N)$ elements of C , and given the RLWE sample c encrypting the polynomial v containing the desired position, the VP uses **BLINDROTATE**($c, \underline{C}, [2^0, 2^1, 2^2, \dots, 2^{\log_2(N)-1}]$) to rotate the desired position to the constant term of v , obtaining an RLWE sample \hat{L} . It then performs **EXTRACTLWE**($\hat{L}, 0$) to extract the desired position to an LWE ciphertext, which is the computation result.

2.5.3 Programmable Bootstrapping. As described in Section 2.5.1, LWE-based encryption requires the addition of a noise (error) component to provide security. This noise grows with every arithmetic operation and eventually needs to reset to some small value to allow for new operations. This process of resetting the noise is a *bootstrapping*. In schemes such as TFHE [16] and FHEW [18], the bootstrapping is implemented as LUT evaluation, which allows one to also use them to evaluate arbitrary functions, a process called *functional bootstrapping* [7], or, more specifically for TFHE, *programmable bootstrapping* [17]. For this work, we see it as just another way of evaluating arbitrary functions represented as LUTs

Algorithm 3: Vertical Packing

Input : a list of k RGSW ciphertexts C , such that each C_i encrypts a message $m_i \in \mathbb{B}$ for $i \in \llbracket 0, k \rrbracket$, where m_i is the bit decomposition of some message $m = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} m_i 2^i$

Input : a list of 2^z RLWE ciphertexts L , each with RLWE dimension N , encrypting a lookup table containing evaluations of some function $f : \mathbb{Z}_{2^k} \mapsto \mathbb{Z}_p$

Output : an LWE sample encrypting $f(m)$

```

1  $n \leftarrow 2^z / 2$ 
2 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $z - 1$  do
3   for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $n$  do
4      $L_j \leftarrow \text{CMUX}(C_i, L_j, L_{j+n})$ 
5    $n \leftarrow n / 2$ 
6  $\hat{L} \leftarrow \text{BLINDROTATE}(L_0, [C_z, \dots, C_k], [2^0, 2^1, \dots, N/4, N/2])$ 
7 return  $\text{EXTRACTLWE}(\hat{L}, 0)$ 

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using TFHE. Different from the VP, it does not require RGSW ciphertexts, being more flexible and allowing its use in composed circuits. On the other hand, it is significantly more expensive and only capable of evaluating small LUTs with good performance.

The evaluation of arbitrary functions using the programmable bootstrapping is broadly explored in the literature [17, 24]. Therefore, we take it as a black-box procedure for the homomorphic evaluation of the following functions:

- **ENCRYPTEDARGMAX**: Given an array of LWE ciphertexts, it returns an LWE ciphertext encrypting the index of the sample with the highest value.
- **ACTIVATE**: Given a function f and an array of LWE ciphertexts encrypting messages m_i , returns an array of LWE ciphertexts encrypting messages $f(m_i)$.

3 HOMOMORPHIC WISARDS

The core procedure in WNNs is the evaluation of RAM units, which can be efficiently evaluated by using some of TFHE’s techniques for LUT evaluation. However, training in WNNs still mixes arithmetic and non-arithmetic operations. Considering this, our first step for homomorphically evaluating WNN is to separate these operations into two independent procedures.

3.1 Integer WiSARDs

Let $\mathcal{W}_{(s,l,a,r)}$ be a WiSARD model as in Definition 1, the Integer WiSARD model follows the same definition with $\mathbb{G} = \mathbb{Z}$ and the training process described in Algorithm 4. Notice that everything remains essentially the same except line 6, which now uses integer RAMs to count occurrences of each input pattern. With this change, the procedure only requires linear arithmetic on each RAM element.

The inference algorithm remains the same as Algorithm 2. By itself, this training process does not provide good accuracy levels. Once the training is finished, we move to a Model Activation step, in which an activation function is applied to each element of each RAM in \mathcal{W} . Notice that together the integer training and RAM activation are functionally equivalent to other WNNs. For example, we can obtain the original wizard by taking a binarization function

Algorithm 4: Integer WiSARD model training

Input : a WiSARD model $\mathcal{W}_{(s,l,a,r)}$

Input : a training set T of size n and its list of labels L

Output : trained Integer WiSARD model

```

1  $\mathcal{W} \leftarrow \{0\}; r \xleftarrow{\mathbb{U}} \mathbb{Z}; k \leftarrow \lceil s/a \rceil;$ 
2 for  $i \in \llbracket 0, n \rrbracket$  do
3    $t \leftarrow \pi_r(T_i)$ 
4   for  $j \in \llbracket 0, k \rrbracket$  do
5      $d \leftarrow f_{\text{comp}}(t, j)$ 
6      $\mathcal{W}[L_i][j][d] \leftarrow \mathcal{W}[L_i][j][d] + 1$ 
7 return  $\mathcal{W}$ 

```

$f_{\text{bin}} : \mathbb{Z} \mapsto \mathbb{B}$, such that $f_{\text{bin}}(x) = 1$ if $x > 0$, and 0 otherwise, as activation. In principle, we propose the model activation as a post-processing to the training, but one could leave it for the inference procedure, which may be more adequate depending on the scenario. It is important to note that, different from typical NNs, the activation process occurs over the model and not over the input data. It is a post-processing procedure, similar, for example, to NN post-training quantization processes [33], which also applies non-linear functions over the NN model.

3.2 Activated WiSARDs

The literature on WNNs often focuses on computationally inexpensive functions to program RAMs, as the goal of employing WNNs is generally to minimize the use of computation resources during training. Binarization and threshold are the main examples of those, and we consider both in our model activation step as a way of evaluating the different existing WNN models. Nonetheless, once we treat the activation as a separate procedure, we can also explore other functions and methods for “activating” the model, obtaining an *Activated WiSARD*. Particularly, our HE evaluation is based on TFHE’s LUT evaluation methods, for which performance depends only on the function precision but not on the specific functions being evaluated.

Considering this, we experiment with more complex activation functions during the model activation procedure. Our main result in this experiment is the introduction of logarithmic activation for WiSARDs. It achieves superior accuracy on problems such as digit recognition on the MNIST dataset compared to traditional binary WiSARD models when using a large set of training samples. Compared to threshold WiSARD models, it incurs a slight accuracy loss, with the advantage of eliminating the need for threshold optimization, a process that may require repeated training, which could introduce a significant slowdown for the encrypted training. Our logarithmic (log) activation is defined as simply applying the $f(x) = \log_2(x + 1)$ function over each integer element of the RAMs of an Integer WiSARD model, whereas the bounded logarithmic (b-log) activation uses the $f(x) = \min(\log_2(x + 1), c)$, which is the \log_2 function with an upper limit value of some (typically small) constant $c > 0$.

3.3 TFHE Building Blocks

The process of evaluating a WiSARD model involves two primary steps: first, evaluating the RAMs, and then, aggregating their outputs to calculate the overall score. Evaluating a sample requires operations that can be easily implemented with standard LUT evaluation procedures from TFHE; Training a sample, on the other hand, requires dynamic LUT modifications to account for the sample. To achieve that, we define a functional inverse for the TFHE’s Vertical Packing procedure, which we introduce in this section.

3.3.1 CDEMUX Gate. The Controlled Demultiplexer gate (CDEMUX) is the functional inverse of TFHE’s Controlled Multiplexer gate (CMUX). It is characterized by two input channels and two output channels: a control input, that receives an RGSW ciphertext encrypting a message in $\mathbb{B} = \{0, 1\}$, and a data input, which receives an RLWE ciphertext. The two data output channels produce RLWE ciphertexts. The CDEMUX gate, through homomorphic computation, directs the input message to either the first or second output channel based on the value of the control input message. Simultaneously, the alternate channel is defined to be an RLWE ciphertext encrypting zero.

For TFHE, the implementation of the CDEMUX gate hinges on the utilization of RGSW-RLWE external products. Mathematically, we formalize the CDEMUX gate : $\text{RGSW} \times \text{RLWE} \mapsto \text{RLWE} \times \text{RLWE}$ as $\text{CDEMUX}(C, d_{in}) := (d_{in} - C \boxtimes d_{in}, C \boxtimes d_{in})$.

3.3.2 CDEMUX Tree. We may extend the CDEMUX gate to incorporate an arbitrary number of output gates by employing a hierarchical, tree-like structure of CDEMUX gates, similar to the CMUX tree in the Vertical Packing. The process initiates with a single CDEMUX operation, followed by successive applications of CDEMUX to both outputs recursively, each tree level utilizing a distinct control message. This approach results in an array composed of RLWE ciphertexts, that is predominantly encrypting zeros, except for one specific coefficient of a specific ciphertext, defined with the value from the input data channel. The position is determined by the values of the control messages used in each level. This technique allows creating an array of any desired size, with precise control over the initialization of a single secret position.

3.3.3 Inverse Vertical Packing. The Inverse Vertical Packing (IVP) technique uses the blind rotation operation and the CDEMUX tree to create an encrypted single-valued LUT following TFHE’s vertical packing encoding. Single-valued LUTs are those composed of zeros except for one secretly designated cell. Complex LUTs can then be created by superimposing multiple single-valued LUTs through RLWE summation. Algorithm 5 details the IVP procedure.

Notice that, since the IVP receives an encrypted RLWE sample as input, it can also be used to arbitrarily update an existing LUT. More specifically, one could use the VP to select an element from the LUT, extract it to an RLWE sample, evaluate arbitrary functions over it, and, finally, use the IVP to move it back to its original position.

3.4 Homomorphic Training

On the client side, we start with a pre-processing phase, where we perform quantization and thermometer encoding over the input data. For each sample, we only consider pre-processing techniques that are independent of the entire dataset. For example, we avoid

Algorithm 5: Inverse Vertical Packing

Input : a list of k RGSW ciphertexts C , such that each C_i encrypts a message $m_i \in \mathbb{B}$ for $i \in \llbracket 0, k \rrbracket$, where m_i is the bit decomposition of some message
 $m = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} m_i 2^i$

Input : an RLWE sample \hat{L} encrypting $f(m)$ for some function $f : \mathbb{Z}_{2^k} \mapsto \mathbb{Z}_p$

Output : a list of 2^z RLWE ciphertexts L , each with RLWE dimension N , encrypting a lookup table containing 0 in all elements except the m -th, which encrypts $f(m)$

```

1  $L_0 \leftarrow \text{BLINDROTATE}(\hat{L}, [C_z, \dots, C_k], [-2^0, -2^1, \dots, -N/4, -N/2])$ 
2  $n \leftarrow 1$ 
3 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $z - 1$  do
4   for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $n$  do
5      $L_j, L_{j+n} \leftarrow \text{CDEMUX}(C_i, L_j)$ 
6    $n \leftarrow 2n$ 
7 return  $L$ 

1 Procedure  $\text{CDEMUX}(C_0, c_1)$ 
2    $\hat{c} = C_0 \boxtimes c_1$ 
3   return  $(c_1 - \hat{c}, \hat{c})$ 

```

techniques such as sample average normalization, which would require knowing data from other samples (which is not always possible in scenarios where data is already encrypted or in cases such as distributed, federated, or continuous learning [42, 49]). Each (quantized) input sample and its label are encrypted bit by bit as RGSW ciphertexts. All data is sent to the server. Definition 2 formalizes the Homomorphic WiSARD Model. Compared to the standard model (Definition 1), the matrix representing this model is rearranged (for compatibility with the vertical packing encoding) and encrypted in RLWE ciphertexts.

DEFINITION 2 (HOMOMORPHIC WiSARD MODEL). *Given a classification problem for encrypted input samples of bit size s and l classes, a Homomorphic WiSARD model $\mathcal{H}_{(s,l,a,r)}$ with address size a and random seed r is a matrix of RLWE ciphertexts in $\text{RLWE}^{k_0 \times k_1}$, such that $k_0 = \lceil s / a \rceil$ is the number of RAMs per discriminator, and $k_1 = \lceil \frac{l 2^a}{N} \rceil$ is the number of RLWE ciphertexts needed to represent a list of l RAMs. Let $\pi_r : \text{RGSW}^s \mapsto \text{RGSW}^s$ be a pseudo-random permutation map for RGSW ciphertexts deterministic on the value of r . Algorithms 6 and 7 present the training and inference on \mathcal{H} .*

We start the Integer training process by initializing with zeros the matrix of RLWE ciphertexts representing the model, and we go over each of the samples in the training set. We apply the random permutation map π_r and partition its result into k_0 vectors of a elements each. These vectors are concatenated with the bits representing the respective label of the sample, producing a vector b of $(a + \log_2 l)$ RGSW samples. Then, we use the IVP procedure over b and an RLWE sample with value 1, which will produce the encrypted single-valued LUT with value 1 at the position determined by b . Finally, this LUT is added to the model.

Algorithm 6: Homomorphic training of the Integer WiSARD model

Input : a Homomorphic WiSARD model $\mathcal{H}_{(s,l,a,r)}$ as defined in Definition 2

Input : a training set T of size n and its list of labels L encrypted bit by bit in RGSW samples

Output : trained Homomorphic Integer WiSARD model

```

1  $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \{0\}; r \xleftarrow{\text{U}} \mathbb{Z};$ 
2  $k_0 \leftarrow \lceil s/a \rceil; k_1 \leftarrow \lceil l2^a/N \rceil$ 
3 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $n - 1$  do
4    $t \leftarrow \pi_r(T_i)$ 
5    $u \leftarrow L_i$ 
6   for  $j \in \llbracket 0, k_0 \rrbracket$  do
7      $b \leftarrow [u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{\lceil \log_2 l \rceil - 1}, t_j, t_{j+1}, \dots, t_{j+a-1}]$ 
8      $h \leftarrow \text{IVP}(b, (0, 1))$ 
9     for  $d \in \llbracket 0, k_1 \rrbracket$  do
10     $\mathcal{H}[j][d] \leftarrow \mathcal{H}[j][d] + h_d$ 
11 return  $\mathcal{H}$ 

```

3.5 Model Activation

Once the Integer training is finished, we start the model activation phase. The goal at this phase is to apply some activation function f_{act} over the values of the Integer WiSARD model. There are a few different approaches to implementing this procedure, which we describe in this section and summarize in Table 1.

approach	cost	model privacy	continuous learning [42]
PD-ACT	very low	\triangle	\checkmark
OTF-ACT	high (eval. time)	\checkmark	\checkmark
FM-ACT	amortized low	\checkmark	\times

Table 1: Comparison between activation approaches.

3.5.1 Post-Encryption Activation (PE-ACT). It is very common to have nonlinear operations at the end of an NN inference process. The most notable example is the use of ARGMAX. When homomorphically evaluating the inference process, a common strategy to deal with these non-linear operations is to send all their inputs to the client, who decrypts them and calculates the operation on the plaintext. This avoids the complexity and computational cost of evaluating non-linear operations at the cost of exposing the output scores of the inference to the client.

The same principle can be adopted for the model activation step of Homomorphic WiSARDs. One can perform the inference process directly over the Homomorphic Integer WiSARD model at the server, retrieve the encrypted score of every LUT, decrypt them individually, and finish the model activation by performing f_{act} , score addition, and ARGMAX on the client. This is the most simple and inexpensive way of performing model activation, but it comes with two downsides:

- Output size: Models are composed of many RAMs. In our experiments, we have up to 6860 RAMs, and each would

produce an encrypted score. At first, this would require many LWE ciphertexts, which in the case of MNIST would use 26.8 MiB of memory. To avoid large result arrays, we can use packing key switch procedure [16] to pack all scores in a single RLWE sample, reducing the usage to 131 KiB.

- Model privacy: Revealing the individual RAM activation results during the evaluation phase enables the client to learn information about the model, that could eventually be used to reconstruct it. While treating this problem is not within the scope of our work, we note it is possible to use simple masking techniques depending on the adopted activation function.

3.5.2 On-the-Fly Activation (OTF-ACT). A second approach for performing the activation is to use TFHE’s programmable bootstrapping (PBS) to evaluate f_{act} over the RAM scores of inference. In this case, one would also perform the inference process directly over the Homomorphic Integer WiSARD model, and use PBS’s to perform f_{act} over the scores, which could then be added to calculate the score of each discriminator. At this point, a sequence of PBS’s can be used to evaluate the encrypted ARGMAX function, and only the inferred class is sent to the client. The main advantage of this approach is fully preserving model privacy as nothing is learned apart from the prediction. It also doesn’t add any cost to the training process. The main downside, on the other hand, is the cost of performing several PBS’s at every inference, which may be acceptable or not, depending on the context.

3.5.3 Full Model Activation (FM-ACT). Finally, the third approach for performing the activation consists of using the PBS to evaluate f_{act} over each element of each RAM of the entire model. The procedure itself is significantly more expensive than the other approaches, but it fully protects model privacy and only needs to run once per model, not affecting inference time. Since the activation is done earlier in the circuit (right after training, instead of after the inference look-up), it may also accelerate the training and inference process by allowing them to use smaller HE parameters (since the noise of the model resets with the bootstrapping). The main downside of this approach is that, once the model is activated, it loses some of the capabilities of the Integer WiSARD model. For example, in a distributed or federated learning scenario, multiple Integer WiSARD models can be merged by simply adding their RAMs. Once the model is activated, the merge becomes dependent on the activation function, which often results in non-linear operations (e.g., when using binarization) or approximations (e.g., when using threshold activation). This approach is also not adequate for continuous learning, as it requires the model to be frequently updated.

3.6 Homomorphic Inference

The homomorphic evaluation of the inference depends on the approach chosen for model activation. Algorithm 7 shows the inference considering these choices. The algorithm goes through every RAM in the model, represented as a vector of RLWE ciphertexts in a line of the model matrix \mathcal{H} . The vector b is the vector of RGSW ciphertexts that serves as input for Vertical Packing. Its first $\log_2(l)$ bits represent the label, as in the training, while the remaining

are part of the encrypted (and now permuted) input. We run the VP for all possible values of labels, accumulating the scores for each class in the vector \hat{u} or saving them in the matrix u for post-decryption activation. Finally, we finish the algorithm depending on the choice of model activation method. Supposing the model was already activated following FM-ACT, we just need to run the homomorphic evaluation of the ARGMAX function. In the case of OTF-ACT, the function ACTIVATE evaluates the activation function over each result of VP using programmable bootstrapping. In the PD-ACT approach, we just pack everything in a single RLWE ciphertext. Masking techniques are optional and dependent on the activation function but could also be applied at this step. Notice that the bits of the label are provided to the VP as cleartext (we are testing every possible label, there's no secret information on them), which makes the computation of the VP much faster than the IVP in the training. On the other hand, we have to run it for every label, which ultimately leads to similar performance between training and inference.

Algorithm 7: Homomorphic inference

Input : a Homomorphic WiSARD Model $\mathcal{H}_{(s,l,a,r)}$
Input : model activation approach FM-ACT, OTF-ACT, or PD-ACT
Input : a sample t encrypted bit by bit in RGSW ciphertexts
Output: classification of t in case of FM-ACT and OTF-ACT, scores of t for every class in case of PD-ACT

```

1  $k_0 \leftarrow \lceil s/a \rceil$ 
2  $t' \leftarrow \pi_r(t)$ 
3  $u \leftarrow \{0\}$ 
4 for  $j \in \llbracket 0, k_0 \rrbracket$  do
5   for  $i \in \llbracket 0, l \rrbracket$  do
6     Let  $\hat{l}$  be the bit decomposition of  $i$  s.t.
7      $i = \sum_{k=0}^{\lceil \log_2 l \rceil - 1} \hat{l}_k 2^k$ 
8      $b \leftarrow [\hat{l}_0, \hat{l}_1, \dots, \hat{l}_{\lceil \log_2 l \rceil - 1}, t_j, t_{j+1}, \dots, t_{j+a-1}]$ 
9     if FM-ACT then
10       $\hat{u}_i \leftarrow \hat{u}_i + \text{VP}(b, \mathcal{H}[j])$ 
11     else if OTF-ACT then
12       $\hat{u}_i \leftarrow \hat{u}_i + \text{ACTIVATE}(f_{act}, \text{VP}(b, \mathcal{H}[j]))$ 
13     else if PD-ACT then
14       $u_{i,j} \leftarrow \text{VP}(b, \mathcal{H}[j])$ 
15 if PD-ACT then
16    $\hat{u} \leftarrow \text{MASK}(u)$ 
17   return PACKINGKEYSWITCHING( $\hat{u}$ )
18 else
19   return ENCRYPTEDARGMAX( $\hat{u}$ )

```

3.7 Additional Techniques

Our evaluation model enables the easy implementation of several additional techniques that are commonly needed for privacy-preserving neural network training and inference. This section discusses some of them.

3.7.1 Dataset Balancing. In a classification problem with l classes, a dataset set with n samples is considered balanced if the number of samples for each class is close to $\lceil n/l \rceil$. While small unbalances are usually not an issue, highly unbalanced datasets are a major problem in neural network training, often leading to skewed models that may even provide artificially high accuracy without solving the actual classification problem [1]. The most straightforward way of solving balancing problems is to use data augmentation techniques on samples of underrepresented classes. Another approach is to adjust the learning rate of the training to correct for the unbalances. For WNNs, the learning rate would be a factor scaling the impact of every sample when programming the RAM. More concretely, in line 6 of Algorithm 4, our learning rate is the value 1, which is the same for all samples. We could add values different from one depending on the class of the input samples. By increasing the value for underrepresented classes, we would be correcting for the dataset unbalance.

Both of these approaches, as well as most of the existing ones for typical neural networks, are problematic for some scenarios of privacy-preserving machine learning. Specifically, to adjust the learning rate one needs to pre-process the data set before starting the training, which may not be possible in scenarios such as distributed or federated learning. It also requires the data set to be fixed before starting the training, which prevents techniques such as continuous learning [42]. Balancing through data augmentation does not present these issues, but it is significantly more expensive to homomorphically evaluate. Considering our Integer WiSARD model is a purely linear algorithm, we present a simple and FHE-friendly alternative for balancing. During training, we use a small IVP over the bits of each sample's label to create an RLWE ciphertext counting the total number of occurrences of each class. This data is then sent to the model activation phase, which will now apply both the activation function and a rescaling according to the encrypted counting of classes. For the PD-ACT this is a trivial procedure, as it can just decrypt the RLWE encrypting the counters and apply the rescaling on cleartext. For encrypted activations, the process is also reasonably straightforward, as the programmable bootstrapping can also be used to apply multivariate functions. More specifically, as introduced in [24] and pointed out in [17], the LUT representing the function to be evaluated by a PBS can be dynamically created using encrypted data, which allows both function composition and multivariate evaluation.

3.7.2 Federated Learning. There are many scenarios where the privacy of multiple parties needs to be simultaneously protected during training or inference. The main example is federated learning [49], a case in which multiple independent (federated) entities collaborate to train a single model together. Each entity has its own privacy concerns and does not want to share input data with the others. This requires the use of techniques such as threshold [4] or multi-key homomorphic encryption [13], which allows computation to be done over data encrypted with different or jointly generated keys. Decryption then becomes a multi-party protocol, in which all involved parties are needed (hence, no data becomes public without the approval of all involved parties). Even more common use cases may have similar requirements. In an encrypted inference running in the public cloud, the owner of the input data

and the owner of the model may be different parties interested in protecting their data (input and model) both from each other as well as from the cloud provider.

Most of the existing literature on encrypted NN training and inference does not consider these aspects, as the techniques required to address them may introduce a significant computation overhead. Even having both the model and input sample simultaneously encrypted might already be prohibitive for some approaches. Homomorphic WiSARDs present many advantages in this regard. Firstly, having the model encrypted only has a minor impact on the inference performance. Specifically, our inference could be 2 to 4 times faster if the model was unencrypted, whereas evaluation models based on other HE schemes may require much larger encryption parameters. Secondly, only the performance of the programmable bootstrapping is affected by the use of threshold HE, whereas other more predominant procedures, such as the VP, are almost unaffected. Specifically, we would need to use bootstrapping methods such as LMK⁺22 [32], which supports multiple parties with a small computational overhead. A third aspect is in the specific case of federated learning. For general neural networks, the complexity of merging the models trained by different federated entities may be a challenging procedure to evaluate homomorphically, as it usually requires rescaling weights and other non-linear procedures. The Integer WiSARD model allows this merge to be performed as a simple addition, which enables one to achieve the same performance as in centralized training (as they are functionally equivalent).

3.7.3 Input Compression. Compared to other methods for training and evaluating Neural Networks, one downside of our evaluation method is the ciphertext expansion of the encrypted input samples. In HE, ciphertext expansion is defined as the factor given by dividing the size of a ciphertext by the size of the data it encrypts.

We use RGSW ciphertexts and bit-by-bit encryption to enable the fast evaluation of the VP and IVP procedures. They are 2ℓ times larger than typical RLWE ciphertexts, and encrypting just one bit per ciphertext introduces an additional $O(N)$ factor to the ciphertext expansion. Conversely, computation using RGSW ciphertexts generates significantly less noise, thus requiring a much smaller ciphertext modulus q . Our approach also does not rely on batching multiple input samples for efficient training and inference, which is an advantage for cases where not all input data is available together at once (e.g., continuous, distributed, or federated learning applications). All in all, our expansion factor varies from $128\ell N$ to $256\ell N$, whereas alternative techniques based on RLWE batched approaches depend on the depth of the network being evaluated, but are usually much smaller. LTB⁺23 [33] reports an expansion factor of $2 \cdot 389/4 \approx 194$ times on a CNN for MNIST with 4-bit linear quantization.

There are many established ways of avoiding or minimizing ciphertext expansion for HE schemes. Notably, one could use trans-ciphering to completely negate ciphertext expansion. For bit-by-bit RGSW encryption, there are also simpler approaches such as packing multiple bits in a single RGSW ciphertext, which allows us to reduce the expansion by a factor of N while only requiring a key switching to unpack the bits. This process is described for the vertical packing in GNA⁺22 [26]. An alternative solution for this problem is to use the other HE schemes and computation

approaches adopted by different NN evaluation methods, which we further discuss in Section 5.1.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We assess the performance of Homomorphic WiSARDs in terms of latency and accuracy across three popular machine learning datasets. Our methodology and comparative approach for these datasets are detailed in this section.

4.1 Datasets

We employed three datasets: MNIST [30], HAM10000 [47], and Wisconsin Breast Cancer [48].

4.1.1 MNIST. The MNIST [30] dataset comprises 70000 grayscale images of handwritten digits, each sized at 28×28 pixels. We follow the standard train and test split and apply linear quantization over the dataset, going from 8 to 4 bits per pixel. We designed four parameter sets to explore parameter scale and sample volume trade-offs. The MNIST_T (tiny), MNIST_S (small), MNIST_M (medium), and MNIST_L (large) are trained over 1000, 7500, 30000 and 60000 samples, respectively.

4.1.2 HAM10000. The HAM10000 [47] dataset, also known as Skin Cancer MNIST or DermaMNIST, consists of 10015 RGB images representing seven types of skin conditions. Here, we use a 80%-20% train-test set split and apply linear quantization, going from 8 to 4 bits per pixel. This dataset is known for being heavily unbalanced [1], and we use our homomorphic balancing technique (Section 3.7.1) to avoid overfitting. The HAM10000_S, HAM10000_M, and HAM10000_L sets have varying computational requirements, and are trained over 1002, 4006, and 8012 samples, respectively.

4.1.3 Wisconsin Breast Cancer. The Wisconsin Breast Cancer [48] dataset comprises 569 samples, featuring 30 attributes of breast cell nuclei, categorized into benign and malignant classes. We employ a 80% train set and 20% test set split, using min-max scaling and linear quantization to convert the features, originally encoded as floating-point numbers, into 8-bit integers. For this dataset, we designed one parameter set, as larger sets yield no improvements.

4.2 Parameter Sets

We performed an extensive search over the TFHE parameter space, namely N , σ , ℓ , and β , to identify sets that could potentially improve performance. The parameter sets used for TFHE, presented in Table 2, were selected to accommodate the required plaintext space \mathbb{Z}_p for each model. The parameter sets of the homomorphic WiSARD models, designed for each dataset, are described in Table 3.

set	σ/q	N	ℓ	β	ℓ_{KS}	β_{KS}
HE ₀	1.1×2^{-51}	2^{11}	1	2^{23}	2	2^{15}
HE ₁			2	2^{15}	3	2^{11}

Table 2: Parameter sets for TFHE. ℓ_{KS} and β_{KS} are decomposition parameters required by PACKINGKEYSWITCHING.

param set	addr	therm		act	thr	encrypt	
		size	type			set	p
MNIST _T	9	4	log	b-log	0	HE ₀	2 ⁸
MNIST _S	12	4	log	b-log	0	HE ₀	2 ¹⁰
MNIST _M	14	4	log	b-log	0	HE ₁	2 ¹²
MNIST _L	16	4	log	b-log	0	HE ₁	2 ¹³
HAM10000 _S	12	5	lin	bin	0	HE ₀	2 ¹⁰
HAM10000 _M	14	5	lin	bin	1	HE ₁	2 ¹³
HAM10000 _L	16	5	lin	bin	1	HE ₁	2 ¹³
Wisconsin	10	5	lin	log	0	HE ₀	2 ⁹

Table 3: Parameter sets for all models, with address sizes, thermometer sizes and types, activation functions, thresholds, TFHE parameter sets, and plaintext moduli.

4.3 Environment Setup

We experiment in two execution environments, one being a consumer Desktop computer with an Intel Core i7-12700k clocked at 5.0 GHz with AVX-512 enabled, 16 threads, and 64GB of memory, and the other an `i4i.metal` instance on AWS with an Intel Xeon Platinum 8375C at 3.5 GHz with 128 threads and 1TB of memory.

4.4 Encrypted Training in the Cloud

We compare the results of our models with the current state-of-the-art for each dataset. Accuracy is given as the average of 100 executions. Lines in **bold** are the results of this work. Evaluation time is always measured for the entire test set, following the division defined in Section 4.1. For these experiments, we consider the PD-ACT activation approach.

4.4.1 MNIST. Our main comparison baseline is Glyph [35], as it represents the current state-of-the-art for encrypted training. We present both their fastest result, obtained with one training iteration (epoch), as well as their highlighted result for better inference. In both cases, we consider only their accuracy results without transfer learning, as we consider it a context-specific optimization that is not in the scope of this work (and which could also be implemented for WNNs [38]). It is unclear whether their reported performance results consider transfer learning, which may be being used to accelerate the training. Glyph [35] runs their experiments in an Intel Xeon E7-8890 v4 at 3.4GHz with 48 threads and 256GB of memory. Therefore, when calculating our speedup over their techniques, we consider both the nominal (raw) values as well as a value adjusted (adj) by the difference in the number of threads. Notice that other factors, such as architecture, CPU frequency, and compiler version, also affect this comparison, but it is difficult to consider these differences without access to their implementation. Table 4 presents the training time and accuracy comparison for our models against Glyph. While we do not implement models with the same accuracy as Glyph, our implementations are significantly faster while only presenting an accuracy drop of 0.4% to 5.4%.

4.4.2 HAM10000. As in the MNIST comparison, we also adjusted the speedup for differences in execution environments between our benchmark and Glyph’s. Another important consideration concerns the balancing of the HAM10000 dataset. As discussed by

model	acc	time	speedup	
			raw	adj
MNIST_S	91.71%	3m28s	3291.4	1234.3
MNIST_M	93.06%	38m18s	300.6	112.7
MNIST_L	93.76%	3h30m	54.9	20.6
Glyph [35]	94.10%	1.5d	5.4	5.4
Glyph [35]	97.10%	8d	1.0	1.0

Table 4: Training time comparison for MNIST.

ASK⁺22 [1], HAM10000 is heavily unbalanced, which often leads to skewed models that may present artificially high accuracies. For example, without balancing, if we split the dataset in its original order (taking the last 20% of the samples as the test set), we achieve 83.37% accuracy because the model completely overfits to a super-represented class, failing to classify all others. As we balance the model, our (artificially high) total accuracy falls significantly, but we are able to better classify some of the underrepresented classes. Glyph [35] does not discuss dataset balancing in their work, so it is unclear whether they addressed this problem. Table 5 presents the results. Different from MNIST, we achieved gains both in performance and accuracy for HAM10000.

model	acc	time	speedup	
			raw	adj
HAM10000_S	67.85%	1m35s	6720.0	2520.0
HAM10000_M	68.60%	13m35s	746.7	280.0
HAM10000_L	69.85%	1h03m	160.0	60.0
Glyph [35]	69.20%	7d	1.0	1.0

Table 5: Training time comparison for HAM10000.

4.4.3 Wisconsin. As this is a much smaller dataset than the others, we are able to compare our technique against alternatives using simpler classification algorithms such as support vector machines (SVM) and multi-layer perception (MLP). Table 6 presents the results. MFK⁺24 [39] run their experiments in an Intel i7-11800H CPU at 4.6GHz with 16 threads whereas PBL⁺20 [43] uses an Intel Xeon CPU E5-2660 v3 at 3.3 GHz with 20 threads. Adjusting for differences in the machines, our model runs from 166 to 1163 times faster than the alternatives with less than 1% accuracy deterioration.

model	acc	time	speedup	
			raw	adj
Wisconsin	97.30%	316ms	9303.8	1163.0
PBL ⁺ 20 SVM [43]	98.00%	5m34s	8.8	7.0
MFK ⁺ 24 MLP [39]	98.25%	49m	1.0	1.0

Table 6: Training time comparison for Wisconsin.

4.5 Small Scale Encrypted Training

To show the practicality of our approach, we conducted benchmarks on a consumer-grade desktop computer, using 1 and 8 threads (each of them assigned to operate on a separate physical core). The times

for medium and large parameter sets were estimated by measuring the execution times across a smaller sample set. Tables 7 and 8 show the execution time and memory consumption for each model. Our main point with this comparison is to show how practical small-scale encrypted training can be, as small datasets require just a few hundred megabytes of memory to run on a single thread.

model	1 thread		8 threads	
	train	eval	train	eval
MNIST _T	12m16s	2h11m	1m33s	19m40s
MNIST _S	2h34m	2h09m	19m19s	18m28s
MNIST _M	28h55m	4h05m	3h41m	33m42s
MNIST _L	156h15m	6h04m	19h57m	48m45s
HAM10000 _S	54m13s	1h24m	6m50s	11m27s
HAM10000 _M	9h19m	2h51m	1h11m	21m11s
HAM10000 _L	43h30m	3h45m	5h27m	29m31s
Wisconsin	11s	3s	1436ms	361ms

Table 7: Consumer desktop benchmark times.

model	1 thread		8 threads	
	train	eval	train	eval
MNIST _T	177MiB	1.0GiB	501MiB	1.1GiB
MNIST _S	427MiB	1.1GiB	2.2GiB	1.1GiB
MNIST _M	1.2GiB	1.8GiB	7.4GiB	1.8GiB
MNIST _L	3.4GiB	3.9GiB	25.1GiB	4.0GiB
HAM10000 _S	638MiB	1.0GiB	3.9GiB	1.1GiB
HAM10000 _M	1.8GiB	2.3GiB	13.1GiB	2.3GiB
HAM10000 _L	6.0GiB	6.2GiB	45.4GiB	6.4GiB
Wisconsin	132MiB	188MiB	146MiB	192MiB

Table 8: Consumer desktop memory usage.

4.6 Model Activation

Sections 4.4 and 4.5 present results considering the PD-ACT activation approach, which is the fastest but relies on masking techniques to fully preserve model privacy. Table 9 presents estimates for the FM-ACT and OTF-ACT approaches considering the use of the programmable bootstrapping as implemented in LW23 [34]. We note that despite working over large plaintext spaces, the activation functions $b\text{-log}$ and bin could be implemented with 9-bit precision for all parameters presented in Table 3 with probability of failure 2^{-9} . The log activation, needed for the Wisconsin problem, already works with $p = 2^9$.

4.7 Encrypted Inference

Table 10 presents the comparison among TFHE-based approaches for encrypted MNIST inference. For our results, we present both single and multi-threaded results (in parentheses). We note that even our single-threaded execution is significantly faster than all other approaches for the same security level.

Model	FM-ACT (hours)		OTF-ACT (min.)	
	9-bit	12-bit	9-bit	12-bit
MNIST _T	0.1	0.4		
MNIST _S	0.4	2.1		
MNIST _M	1.1	6.4		
MNIST _L	3.8	22.0		
HAM10000 _S	0.9	5.0	3.7	21.3
HAM10000 _M	2.8	16.4		
HAM10000 _L	9.8	57.2		
Wisconsin	0.1	0.4		

Table 9: Estimated execution time of other model activation approaches. FM-ACT is the time for activating the full model given in hours, estimated for 64 threads. OTF-ACT is the time to activate the result of each inference given in minutes, estimated for a single thread. Both consider the PBS execution time from LW23 [34].

model	acc	time (s)	sec (λ)	threads
DiNN [8]	93.71	0.49	80	1
DiNN [8]	96.3	1.5	80	1
SFB ⁺ 23 [45]	92.2	31	128	16
SFB ⁺ 23 [45]	96.5	77	128	16
SHE [36]	99.54	9.3	128	20
REDsec [20]	98	12.3	128	96
REDsec [20]	99	18.4	128	96
MNIST_S	91.4	0.774 (0.048)	128	1 (128)
MNIST_M	92.81	1.47 (0.067)	128	1 (128)
MNIST_L	93.43	2.184 (0.092)	128	1 (128)

Table 10: Comparison of encrypted inference execution time for TFHE-based approaches for the MNIST dataset. The security level (λ) is expressed in bits.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced the homomorphic evaluation of WNN training and inference algorithms, as well as supporting procedures, such as homomorphic dataset balancing. While WNNs may not still reach the same accuracy levels as CNNs, we showed they are capable of achieving good accuracy levels in just a few minutes of encrypted training, a considerable advance compared to the several days of computation required by previous works. We also showed they have many other advantages besides performance. They can be easily employed for distributed, federated, and continuous learning applications, scenarios that often require major modifications for other types of networks. There are also many opportunities to further improve their performance and accuracy.

5.1 Further Improvements

Transfer Learning. A major opportunity for future research is the adoption of transfer learning techniques for WNNs. Glyph [35] used transfer learning to improve their CNN results, reporting an increase of up to 4% in accuracy for HAM10000 and 2% for MNIST. Recently, PTC24 [41] employed transfer learning to fine-tune encrypted image recognition models, obtaining further performance

and accuracy improvements over Glyph. Transfer learning techniques have also been successfully used for WNNs. MAG⁺18 [38] achieved an up to 11.2% accuracy improvement over previous literature using transfer learning on a WiSARD for an image classification problem. Compared to their own WiSARD model without transfer learning, the improvement was more than 40%.

Multi-shot Learning. Other techniques that may improve WNN-based models are the multi-shot training procedures such as back-propagation, utilized in the ULEEN [46] framework. While individual techniques from their models were also tested into our models, they did not yield any improvements without this specific training technique. Given that their models achieve up to 98.5% accuracy on the MNIST dataset, integrating this technique could potentially narrow the gap between encrypted WNNs and conventional state-of-the-art CNNs.

Horizontal Packing. Horizontal packing [15] is a technique that complements TFHE vertical packing by allowing the evaluation of multiple LUTs at once. It is particularly useful for LUTs with sizes smaller than the HE parameter N . For large datasets such as the MNIST and HAM10000, small RAMs didn't show good accuracy levels, but they seem to be adequate for smaller problems, such as Wisconsin. For those, horizontal packing can be employed to allow the evaluation of RAMs from different discriminators simultaneously.

WNNs and other encryption schemes. TFHE excels among other HE schemes by its capabilities of efficiently evaluating LUTs. However, other schemes, such as BFV [9, 19], BGV [10], and CKKS [14] are also capable of doing so. They generally present much higher latency for performing functional bootstrapping, but their throughput of operations may even surpass TFHE's [34]. Conversely, evaluating larger LUTs with similar performance levels as the Vertical Packing still seems to be a challenge for them. Nonetheless, it should be practical to evaluate WNNs using these schemes at least for problems requiring relatively smaller RAMs (e.g., Wisconsin).

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